

Supplementary Figure S1. Whole-body and pancreas weight measurements in C57BL/6 mice experimental cohorts. **A.** Dot plot representing mice body weights with the effect of alcohol withdrawal/continuation during the recovery phase of A, CP, and ACP induction (3- and 21-days period). **B.** Relative body weight measurement with alcohol withdrawal/continuation effect during the recovery phase of 21 days after initial ACP induction. **C.** Relative pancreas weight measurement with alcohol withdrawal/continuation effect during the recovery phase of 3 and 21 days of ACP induction in C57BL/6 mice.

A

Supplementary Figure S2. Effects of alcohol withdrawal or the continuation after 21 days of recovery phase on mice pancreatic architecture with established ACP. **A.** Representative immunofluorescence image of mice pancreas showing significant loss of acinar cell positivity with persistent damage with the continuation of alcoholic diet during the recovery period of 21 days post ACP induction compared to mice without alcohol. **B.** Quantitative histological assessment of collagen deposition using trichrome blue staining analysis on pancreatic tissue sections obtained from control and ACP with 21 days of recovery with and without alcohol.

Supplementary Figure S3. Effects of Uro A treatment on established ACP with continued alcohol intake. **A.** Relative pancreas weight measurement during treatment regimen of Uro A with ACP induction (with the effect of alcohol withdrawal/continuation) in C57BL/6 mice. **B.** Western blot analysis demonstrated increased pAKT activation with ACP induction as compared to controls in the pancreatic tissue lysates. Treatment with Uro A resulted in a significant reduction in the activated levels of pAKT associated with ACP induction within the mouse pancreas harvested after 3 days and 2 weeks of recovery period despite continued alcohol trigger.

Supplementary Figure S4. Effects of Uro A treatment on fibrosis in established ACP with continued alcohol exposure. Quantitative histological assessment of collagen deposition using trichrome blue staining analysis on pancreatic tissues sections obtained from control, ACP, ACP+Uro A with the effect of alcohol withdrawal/continuation during the 2 weeks of recovery period.